

IMPLEMENTATION OF A VISCOELASTIC MATERIAL MODEL TO PREDICT THE COMPACTION RESPONSE OF DRY CARBON FIBRE PREFORMS

Bublitz Dennis ^{a,*}, Colin David ^a, Drechsler Klaus ^a

^a Chair of Carbon Composites, TUM School of Engineering & Design, Department of
Aerospace and Geodesy, Chair of Carbon Composites, Boltzmannstr. 15, 85748 Garching,
Germany

*Corresponding author: dennis.bublitz@tum.de

ABSTRACT

Determining the compaction behavior of fibrous material is essential for fiber reinforced composites manufacturing processes. The compression state directly influences both fiber volume content and tooling forces in closed mold processes. In this work, we present a viscoelastic material model which describes the compaction stress response. In its incremental formulation, the model is implemented into a finite element code, which makes it possible to calculate the thickness of force-controlled setups. We derived model parameters from compaction experiments with woven and non-crimp fabric carbon fiber preforms. The predicted compaction stress for both materials was in good agreement with the experimental data. Moreover, the model is capable of predicting creep and spring back behavior for force-controlled experiments. We proved that the developed model can be used to eliminate peak stresses during compaction and is also capable of predicting the time-dependent thickness response by means of a single set of formulas.

KEYWORDS

A. Preform, B. Stress relaxation, C. Numerical analysis, E. Resin transfer moulding (RTM)

1 INTRODUCTION

Liquid composite molding (LCM) processes are widely used in the aerospace and automotive industries to produce high quality carbon fiber reinforced plastic parts at high manufacturing rates. One important factor for predicting the final part quality and optimizing the manufacturing process is the distribution of the final fiber volume content (FVC) in the part. This property is mainly influenced by the compression of the preform due to the applied pressure or the tool closing in case of a closed mold process. In complex shaped preforms, compaction gradients can occur due to friction during the tool closing [1]. The degree of compaction of the preform has a major influence on the subsequent infiltration. On the one hand, the FVC directly influences the permeability of the preform. The resin flows more slowly in highly compacted areas than in other sections. On the other hand, over-compacted areas in small radii can lead to empty regions in the cavity in closed mold processes such as resin transfer molding (RTM). During the resin injection, these gaps can act as unwanted flow channels in the RTM tool [1,2]. Merging flow fronts, which are induced by race-tracking channels, can lead to dry spots in the final part. Moreover, the fiber volume fraction has an influence on residual stresses and part distortion [3,4]. Especially in complex and thin-walled structures, the FVC gradient is a main driver for process induced distortions [5].

This work focuses on the development of a material model which describes the compaction behavior of dry carbon fiber preforms. The objective is to find a formulation which is capable of predicting tooling forces in closed mold processes, and can also calculate the thickness distribution of the preform. In order to be able to calculate

displacement-controlled as well as force-controlled scenarios, the model is implemented in a user subroutine for numerical simulations.

A model of the material behavior in the thickness direction is essential for predicting tooling forces and the preform shape after compaction. Experimental investigations on the compaction behavior of textile reinforcements exhibit a time-dependent stress response. Woven fabrics, random mats, and non-crimp fabrics made of various kinds of fibers exhibit an exponential stress increase during compaction and stress relaxation during the holding phase [6–11]. The compaction phase of preforms can be divided into three sections. The first linear section is caused by local compaction and the closing of large voids due to nesting, which is followed by nonlinear compression of the yarns and yarn bending deformation [11–13]. In the last section, almost no voids remain and no further rearrangements take place, thus causing an almost linear rapid stress increase [13]. The stress release during the relaxation phase can be explained by the reorientation of the bended fibers after the compaction [11,14].

Compaction experiments are generally performed between two compaction plates in a universal testing machine. The high force acting during compression at high fiber volume contents causes both the testing machine and the specimen to deform. As a result, the displacement measurement from the testing machine can provide significant errors at high forces. Several authors used displacement sensors [10,15,16] or video analysis [17] to measure the deflection of the upper compaction plate. Other authors have used the displacement of the cross head for the thickness measurement without mentioning measures accounting for testing machine deformation [15,18–20].

The results from experimental characterization tests were used to develop models which are capable of describing the material behavior. Mathematical descriptions of the stress response of viscoelastic materials are mostly based on a generalized Maxwell model. One general nonlinear viscoelastic model for polymeric materials has been presented by Schapery [21]. This three-dimensional model is based on thermodynamic principles. Besides nitrocellulose and polyisobutylene, he also applied his model to fiber-reinforced phenolic resin. Schapery's model has been further used for finite element implementations [22,23]. Kaliske et al. [24] formulated a recursive three-dimensional model for viscoelastic materials. The model is based on a generalized Maxwell model with linear elastic springs. According to the authors, the incremental formulation of the model allows an efficient implementation in a finite element code for large-scale models. In later studies, the authors have focused on the development of compaction models for fibrous preforms. Kim et al. [20] performed compression tests on various reinforcement materials. They fitted the relaxation curves to a Maxwell-Wiechert model, which corresponds to the generalized Maxwell model without the free spring. Kelly et al. [15] investigated the viscoelastic compaction behavior of continuous glass filament mats. They modeled the compaction and relaxation using a generalized Maxwell model with nonlinear elastic elements. The formulation of branch stresses in their model is derived from a thermomechanical model. More recently, Kelly [25] presented a model based on the decomposition of strain- and strain rate-dependent stresses, in which compression and relaxation responses are modeled separately. According to the author, the model only applies for materials with normalized stress curves which collapse to a single master curve. Another model for the compaction response of various glass fiber reinforcements has been described by Somashekar et al. [26]. Their application of a generalized Maxwell model with linear springs and dashpots does not account for different compaction velocities. Yenilmez et al. [27] compared different viscoelastic models and analyzed their capabilities for predicting the compaction behavior of woven fabrics. They found that Burgers and generalized Maxwell models had the highest performance. Danzi et al. [28] published a compaction model for woven carbon fiber fabrics. Their formulation uses a single formula for compression and relaxation, which is based on a generalized Maxwell model with nonlinear springs and dashpots. They used a Heaviside function in order to activate a second term for the stress relaxation after the compression

step. Since the strain rate is not defined as a function of time, the model is only applicable for constant velocities during the compression phase.

The aforementioned models are based on formulations used to calculate the stress response for a given strain rate. For the prediction of the preform thickness at a defined stress state, the equations need to be solved for the current strain. Due to their complexity, most of the formulations can only be solved numerically.

Bickerton and Kelly [29] used the viscoelastic model presented in [15] for an implementation in a finite element analysis to predict tooling forces in an RTM process. They extended the model to complex geometries by adding a shear stress component. There are further applications of viscoelastic compaction models in finite element applications [30–32]. These applications are limited to the prediction of tooling forces in liquid composite molding processes. Moreover, the models have not been validated for non-constant tool closing velocities, which are crucial for describing the deformation in an industrial RTM process.

Models have been presented which are capable of predicting the shape of fibrous materials in force-controlled setups. Models describing the consolidation of prepregs, which also show a viscoelastic behavior similar to dry fabrics, have considered the deformation of the fiber bed and the resin viscosity [33,34]. Predicting the preform thickness in force-controlled setups is of special importance for simulations of compression RTM processes. Most of the currently available models use nonlinear elastic models (without time dependency) for calculating the preform thickness [35–37]. As a result, they are not capable of predicting creeping or material spring-back. Verley et al. [38] modeled force-controlled RTM processes using an iterative method to solve the viscoelastic model from [25]. This model uses two separate formulas for compaction and relaxation. Thompson et al. [39] used a combination of shell and membrane elements to model the compaction defects in thick layups. They used a nonlinear elastic penalty stiffness of the intra-ply contacts without time dependency to account for the through thickness behavior of the preform.

Most of the existing models focus on the compaction or the relaxation behavior. Some models provide two separate formulas or combine them with a Heaviside function. We assume that the two phases cannot always be clearly separated, especially for setups with a smooth transition from the compaction to the relaxation phase. To the authors knowledge the model from Kelly et al. [15] is the only one which describes the two phases in a single formula. Nevertheless, none of the models presented have been applied and validated so as to predict the stress response as well as the thickness of preforms. Moreover, none of the aforementioned models has been implemented in order to calculate time-dependent material spring-back. A thorough description of the material behavior in a single equation is crucial for predicting the material response to arbitrary or combined forces and displacement loads.

In the present study, specimens of different materials were manufactured under process conditions to predict tooling forces and the final preform shape in injection processes. We implemented a new compaction model in a user-subroutine which describes compaction and relaxation in a single formula via the finite element software ANSYS. We performed a parameter study in order to identify the necessary number of independent variables and calibrated the model using the set of parameters derived. In the next step, we applied the model to force-controlled compaction setups and validated it against experiments with a weave and a non-crimp fabric (NCF).

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 MATERIALS

HexForce G0926 [40] woven fabric and biaxial NCF Tenax-E DRNF PB1 [41] were used for the compaction experiments. The carbon fiber satin weave consisted of 6 k rovings and had 2.5% epoxy powder E01 on each side with an areal weight AW of 375 g/m². The NCF material consisted of two $\pm 45^\circ$ layers with 24 k carbon fiber

rovings and stitching yarns in a tricot pattern. 1.7% powder binder EP05311 were located on the top side of the material. The areal weight of the NCF was 388 g/m².

Both materials were cut into squares of 440 mm x 440 mm using a CNC-cutting machine and then stacked to a symmetric twelve-layer cross-ply laminate. Every second layer was rotated by 90° with two layers of the same orientation in the middle of the preform. The stacked layups were preformed in a hot press with 600 mm x 600 mm plates at 100 °C. For the weave material, a force of 1000 kN was applied for 30 seconds. The NCF was preformed with 580 kN force for 120 seconds. In both cases, steel shims with 8.0 mm were used to ensure a uniform sample thickness. The preforms were cooled at room temperature. After preforming, 20 mm was cut from every edge to avoid fringed areas in the preforms. The remaining samples were cut into 16 specimens sized 100 mm x 100 mm using the CNC cutting machine. The weave specimens had an average thickness of 8.05 mm with a standard deviation of 0.11 mm, and 6.81 mm with a standard deviation of 0.06 mm for the NCF specimens.

2.2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND PROCEDURE

A UPM 250 universal testing machine from Hegewald und Peschke with a 250 kN load cell was used for the compaction tests. Two square steel plates with a length of 220 mm ensured a uniform pressure distribution on the surface of the specimen (see

Figure 1). A videoextensometer with a telecentric lens, which can be seen in the background, measured the distance between the two plates during the experiment. Preliminary tests showed that the test machine deformed significantly at higher stresses and a high FVC. At a force of 20 kN, the displacement recorded by the machine differed by 0.16 mm from the videoextensometer measurement. Due to the machine deformation, the cross-head velocity decreased during the compaction from 5 mm/min to 3 mm/min, when the force reached 20 kN. In order to ensure a constant upper plate speed during the compression, the position of the crosshead was both measured and controlled by the displacement signal of the videoextensometer. A constant compression speed was essential for the parameter fitting because the optimization algorithm uses constant velocities.

Figure 1: Experimental setup of the compaction experiments

The procedure of the displacement-controlled tests started with a compaction to an initial thickness of 7.6 mm for the weave and 6.7 mm for the NCF material. The corresponding mean pre-compaction force was 25 N for the weave and 1.4 N for the NCF. This compensated for potential variability of the preform thickness after manufacturing and ensured a uniform starting point for all specimens of the same material. Given that the specimens experienced different degrees of compaction in reaching the initial FVC, the stresses were relaxed for two minutes. The compression to the final FVC then started. The compression speed was constant until reaching the final thickness. The final position was held constant for ten minutes in order to measure the stress relaxation.

At the end of the experiment, the plates opened at a constant speed. This compaction test was repeated for six different configurations of each material at different compaction velocities and different final fiber volume fractions. Table 1 provides an overview of these configurations. Each configuration was repeated with five test samples. The FVC, in dependency of the preform thickness h , can be described as follows:

$$V_f = \frac{N \cdot AW}{\rho_{fiber} \cdot h} \quad (1)$$

Where N is the number of plies in the preform, AW is the areal weight, and ρ_{fiber} is the fiber density. With $\rho_{fiber}=1,77\text{g/cm}^3$ [40] and the initial thickness $h=7.6$ mm, the initial FVC of the weave can be calculated as 0.34. A fiber density $1,78\text{g/cm}^3$ [41] and an initial thickness of $h=6.7$ mm lead to an initial FVC of 0.39 for the NCF.

Table 1: Displacement-controlled experiments of the weave (WV) and the NCF materials

<i>Configuration</i>	<i>Final FVC [-]</i>	<i>Compaction velocity [mm/min]</i>	<i>Final thickness weave [mm]</i>	<i>Final thickness NCF [mm]</i>
WV_0.45-2 / NCF_0.45-2	0.45	2.0	5.65	5.81
WV_0.50-1 / NCF_0.50-1	0.50	1.0	5.08	5.23
WV_0.50-2 / NCF_0.50-2	0.50	2.0	5.08	5.23
WV_0.50-5 / NCF_0.50-5	0.50	5.0	5.08	5.23
WV_0.55-1 / NCF_0.55-1	0.55	1.0	4.62	4.76
WV_0.55-2 / NCF_0.55-2	0.55	2.0	4.62	4.76
WV_0.55-5 / NCF_0.55-5	0.55	5.0	4.62	4.76
WV_0.60-2 / NCF_0.60-2	0.60	2.0	4.23	4.36

Similar experiments were conducted for force-controlled tests. Instead of constant compression velocity, a constant force rate compacted the preforms. The distance of the compaction plates was measured using the videoextensometer. Additionally to configurations 0.50-1 and 0.50-5, which were not used for the model calibration, the force-controlled experiments were used for the model validation. Since the model was being used to predict the final thickness of preforms after compaction, the applicability had to be proved with force-controlled setups. As for the displacement-controlled tests, the specimens were compacted to an initial fiber volume fraction of 0.34 or 0.39. The preforms were compacted at a constant force rate of 100 N/s and 250 N/s, respectively. The force was kept constant for ten minutes after reaching the maximum of 10 kN for the weave material. The NCF was compacted with a maximum force of 4.2 kN. Measuring the thickness evolution at a constant force enabled the quantification of material creep. At the end of the experiment, the force was released at a constant rate of 20 N/s for the slow compacted specimens, and 50 N/s for the faster compaction. The release rate was lower than that of the compaction in order to guarantee continuous contact between the plate and the preform.

2.3 RESULTS

Figure 2a shows the results of the displacement-controlled experiments with the weave material. Besides the mean curve, the minimum and maximum values at every time point are displayed as scatter areas in the graphs. The coefficient of variation is between 2.6% and 8.1% of the mean curve. The curves with the same final fiber volume fraction indicate that the peak stresses slightly increase at an increasing compaction speed. The compaction responses of these curves did not relax to the same final stress. For the 50% final FVC, the curves show lower

absolute relaxed stresses for lower compaction velocities. For the 55% final FVC, the fastest compaction results in the lowest absolute relaxed stress. The evolution of the relaxed stress in dependency of the fiber volume fraction was clearly non-linear. The relation between FVC and relaxed stress seems to be exponential.

The results of the displacement-controlled experiment configurations from Table 1 of the NCF are shown in Figure 2b. In comparison with the weave material, the general stress level is significantly lower. Moreover, the scattering of the results is lower compared to the weave material. The coefficient of variation of the NCF is between 1.9% and 4.6% of the mean curve. Furthermore, the qualitative behavior differed from the weave material. During the relaxation, the stress in the NCF preforms decreased by only approximately 30%. In contrast, about 60% of the peak stresses were relaxed for the lower three analyzed FVC of the weave material. For the NCF, the relaxed stresses at 50% and 55% FVC were lower when the material was compacted at a higher velocity. The same effect was observed for the weave material at 55% FVC.

Figure 2: Experimental data for different compaction velocities and final FVC, including minimum and maximum scatter area; (a) weave material; (b) NCF material

Figure 9 shows the results of the force-controlled experiments with the weave material. The curves represent the average of five repetitions. The shaded area describes the scatter in which all the single results lay. The coefficient of variation was 1.3% for the low force rate and 0.9% for the high force rate. A creep effect was observable when the force was held at a constant value. For faster compaction, the preforms reached a higher FVC. During the release of the force, the preforms exhibited a spring-back behavior to a higher thickness. A similar behavior was observable for the force-controlled experiments with the NCF material in Figure 10. Likewise, the material became slightly more compacted at a higher force rate. As in the displacement-controlled experiments, the scattering was lower for the NCF material. The coefficient of variation was 0.55% and 0.20% of the mean curve for the low force rate and the high force rate, respectively.

Measurements of the thickness of the specimen shortly after the compaction experiment showed that the preforms did not reach the initial state. Weave preforms having an average initial thickness of 8.1 mm were compacted to 5.1 mm and showed a spring-back to 7 mm shortly after the experiment. One hour later, the thickness increased to 7.6 mm, which corresponded to an average recovery of 83% of the maximum compaction strain. There thus appeared to be an extremely slow spring-back or an irreversible part of the deformation corresponding to a small plastic contribution in addition to the elastic and viscous behaviors on a macroscale. On a smaller scale, this can be explained by irreversible nesting effects or the permanent rearrangement of fibers. Another effect could

have been be the permanent deformation of the binder network. In this study, only the spring back behavior of preforms shortly after the compaction with the maximum force was characterized and modeled. Therefore, the contribution of the plasticity was neglected for the materials analyzed in this work. Regarding long-term effects or different materials, plasticity might be relevant or can be modeled with an additional viscous element with an extremely long relaxation time.

The scatter of experiments can be explained with different nesting conditions in the specimens. Lomov et al. [42] showed that random nesting has a significant influence on the fiber volume fraction and the scatter of permeability. Chen and Chou [43] presented a unit-cell model for multi-layer preforms showing the influence of different nesting configurations on the compaction pressure. Nesting was not reproducible during the layup of large preforms. A variation in the nesting thus leads to different compaction responses. This also explains the lower scattering of the experimental data of the NCF compared to the weave material due to less potential nesting between the individual layers. Because of the roving undulations in the weave material, the degree of nesting can vary in a larger range, which can lead to more differing material responses.

3 MODEL DEVELOPMENT

3.1 FITTING APPROACH

A phenomenological approach was used to modify an existing model in order to better reproduce the experimental data. The starting point of the model development was a generalized Maxwell model in which the branch spring stiffness E_j was modified with different formulations. The resulting models were fitted to the test results. For this purpose, we used an optimization algorithm which minimizes the area between experimental and model curves. The quality of a certain formulation was evaluated using the results of the objective function. The fitting algorithm reads in the experimental time - stress data and takes the same time steps to calculate the total stress with the developed model. The difference from the experimental curve can then be calculated without interpolation. For every input curve, the difference between experimental and model stress was calculated for each data point. The normalized sum of the stress differences λ for one input curve was calculated as follows:

$$\lambda = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^P (\sigma_{i,exp} - \sigma_{i,model})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^P \sigma_{i,exp}^2} \quad (2)$$

The square difference between experiment and model was summed up for every stress data point σ_i . P describes the total number of data points of the current curve. The square difference method was used in order to give areas with greater deviation a higher weight in the optimization. The value was normalized to the square sum of the experimental values to make an evaluation of the quality of a fit at the different stress levels possible. By summing up the normalized stress differences for all input curves, the objective function is defined as follows:

$$\lambda_{tot} = r \cdot \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{(\sigma_{min,exp} - \sigma_{min,model})_k^2}{\sigma_{min,exp,k}^2} + (1 - r) \cdot \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k \quad (3)$$

The stress difference λ_{tot} for all input curves k was minimized. M is the number of input curves which are selected for the optimization. In order to receive a better representation of the peak stress, the difference between the minimum stresses σ_{min} of each curve receives a higher weight in the objective function. Therefore, the absolute difference between the experimental and model peak stress was considered with a weighting factor r . A weight $r = 0.1$ for the peak stress has been found to produce the best results. The normalized total difference λ_{tot} was minimized with a sequential least squares programming method implemented in Python.

3.2 FORMULATION OF SPRING STIFFNESS

The development of a new model capable of predicting the compaction behavior of carbon fiber preforms was based on the formulation from Kaliske et al. [24]. They used a generalized Maxwell model to describe the viscoelastic behavior of different rubber materials. The main advantage of their model is that compaction and relaxation can be described with a single formula. Moreover, the analytical solution provides the option of a computational efficient implementation in an FEA code.

The stress h_j in one Maxwell branch j is given by an incremental formulation in dependency of the previous time step [24]:

$$h_j^{n+1} = \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_j}\right) \cdot h_j^n + E_j \cdot \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_j}\right)\right) \frac{\Delta \epsilon}{\Delta t / \tau_j} \quad (4)$$

Where Δt is the time step size, τ is the relaxation time of the dashpot, E is the stiffness of the spring, and ϵ is the total strain of the Maxwell element.

The total stress σ is defined as the sum of the N branch stresses and the stress in the free spring with stiffness E_0 [24]:

$$\sigma^{n+1} = E_0 \epsilon^{n+1} + \sum_{j=1}^N h_j^{n+1} \quad (5)$$

The stiffness E_0 in the free spring ensured that not all of the applied stress was relaxed after the compaction. The magnitude of relaxed stresses of the various configurations in Figure 2 increases sharply with an increasing final FVC. The relation between relaxed stress and FVC was thus strongly non-linear. Consequently, we introduced an expression of the stiffness E_0 with an exponential law in dependency of the fiber volume fraction V_f .

$$E_0 = \frac{A}{V_f} \cdot \exp(B \cdot V_f^2) \quad (6)$$

The variables A and B are fitting parameters which can be derived from the relaxed stresses depending on the final FVC.

With a defined E_0 , a novel formulation which describes the stress in one branch can then be developed. Initially, the aforementioned model from Kalsike with three Maxwell branches and a constant spring stiffness E_j was implemented in Python. In order to evaluate the capabilities of the model, it was fitted to configuration WV_0.55-1 of the weave material using Eq. (3). The resulting curve was plotted in Figure 3a (referred to as “const”) together with the mean value of the experimental data. The fit of the *const* model shows that the exponential stress increase during the compaction phase cannot be well reproduced. Moreover, the model provides a poor fit of the high peak stress. However, the relaxed stress was described very well, which is defined by the stiffness E_0 . In order to gain a deeper understanding of the reason why the model was not capable of showing high peak stresses, it was fitted again with a higher weight for the peak stress, $r = 0.99$. The resulting curve is shown in Figure 3a as “const peak”. This modification led to a very good description of the peak stress and the stress decrease during relaxation. However, the compaction phase was modeled extremely poorly. The significant difference compared to the experimental curve in the first phase led to higher values λ_{tot} of the objective function during the optimization. The deviation of the model during the compaction phase can be explained by the evolution of the branch stresses. Figure 3b shows the contributions of the four branches to the total stress for the *const peak* fit. Due to the constant FVC in the holding phase, the stress in E_0 remained constant. Thus, high peak stresses could only be achieved with high stresses in the remaining branches. In every branch, the stress increases sharply at the

beginning when the deformation is mostly taken by the spring. Since the dashpot takes larger fractions of the deformation, the stress increased more slowly. During the holding phase, the extension of the spring reached its initial state, and the stress returned to zero. The higher the peak stress compared to the relaxed stress of the experimental data, the higher the fraction from the branches in the model needs to be. However, this also caused larger deviations in the compaction phase. Hence, the *const* model might be suitable for materials with low peak stresses, but not for high peak stresses.

Since the stiffness was constant, the elastic branch strains had the same qualitative behavior as the branch stresses shown in Figure 3b. The slope of the branch stress can be adjusted by modifying the stiffness E_j . Thus, in order to achieve a better fit during the compaction phase, a non-linear stiffness with a flat increase at the beginning and a steep increase towards the peak stress is needed. With a spring and a dashpot connected in series, the viscous strain shows this qualitative behavior. Given that the strain in the dashpot equals the total strain minus the elastic strain, it has the opposite behavior of the strain in the spring. The *viscous lin* model uses a stiffness with a linear dependency on the viscous strain. The best fit of this model is shown in Figure 3a. Contrary to the two fits with a constant stiffness, the compaction showed a good agreement with experimental results. The peak stress was significantly higher than with the *const* model, but still not as high as the experimental data. The relaxation phase was in good agreement with the test, but the stress was relaxing too slowly. In order to further improve the fit, the stiffnesses E_j were defined with an exponential dependency on the viscous strain. The result of the fitting optimization is shown in Figure 3a. The *viscous exp* model is in very good agreement with the experimental data in the compaction phase as well as in the relaxation phase. A comparison of the best fit results for the four different models is given in Table 2. The optimized values of the objective function support that the *viscous exp* model agrees extremely well with the experimental data. As a result, only this model was considered for the following study.

Table 2: Comparison of the fit optimization for different stiffness formulations

<i>model</i>	E_j formulation	λ_{tot} of best fit
<i>const</i>	$E_j = a_j$	$21.29 \cdot 10^{-3}$
<i>const peak</i>	$E_j = a_j$	$94.33 \cdot 10^{-3}$
<i>viscous lin</i>	$E_j = a_j \cdot \epsilon^v$	$4.488 \cdot 10^{-3}$
<i>viscous exp</i>	$E_j = a_j \cdot \exp(b_j \cdot \epsilon^v)$	$0.9438 \cdot 10^{-3}$

In order to account for the stiffnesses E_j , which can vary between two consecutive time steps, Eq. (4) was adjusted. The consideration of the time dependency of the stiffness for the integration leads to:

$$h_j^{n+1} = \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_j}\right) \cdot h_j^n + \left(E_j^{n+1} - E_j^n \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_j}\right)\right) \frac{\Delta \epsilon}{\Delta t / \tau_j} \quad (7)$$

With the total strain ϵ and the elastic branch strain ϵ_j^e , the branch stiffness can be written as:

$$E_j = a_j \cdot \exp((\epsilon - \epsilon_j^e) \cdot b_j) \quad (8)$$

Where a_j and b_j are constants relative to the branch stiffness. For the calculation of the current stress, the stiffness E_j^{n+1} needs to be known and depends on the strain $\epsilon_j^{e,n+1}$. From Eq. (7), a formulation for the current elastic strain can be derived:

$$\epsilon_j^{e,n+1} = \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_j}\right) \cdot \epsilon_j^{e,n} + \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_j}\right)\right) \frac{\Delta \epsilon}{\Delta t / \tau_j} \quad (9)$$

The total stress in the system can be calculated with Eq. (5) by inserting Eq. (6), (7), (8), and (9). The model is described with the fitting parameters A and B for the spring E_0 and the parameters a_j , b_j , and τ_j for each branch.

The derivation of Eq. (4) was based on the assumption of linear elastic behavior. Given that a non-linearity has been introduced later on in order to improve the accuracy of the model, the new formulation does not correspond to a generalized Maxwell model. Thus, the stress which is calculated with Eq. (7) is not the same as the stress of a non-linear Maxwell model with the branch stiffness of Eq. (8). The solution of this non-linear problem would not provide a simple analytical solution. The derivation of the stress formulation requires a time integration of the relaxation function, which leads to extremely complex equations if the stiffness itself is time dependent. A numerical integration is possible, but it results in very long calculation times. However, the goal of this study is to provide a numerically efficient model capable of predicting the behavior of the material. Hence, a phenomenological approach for the derivation of this model was chosen.

Figure 3: (a) Experimental stress evolution of config 0.55-1 in comparison with different model formulations; (b) Branch stresses of the const peak fit compared to experimental stress data of config WV_0.55-1

The recursive formulation of the presented model takes the current strain and the strain rate as inputs for each time increment. This formulation thus enables the calculation of stresses for non-constant compaction velocities. This is useful in case the tool velocity is decreased before the maximum stress is reached in order to minimize peak stresses. The model can also be applied to compute stresses for multi-step compaction processes. The derivation of the model parameters requires two steps. In the first step, the relaxed stresses for different FVC are fitted to Eq. (6). With the derived values for A and B , the remaining branch parameters a_j , b_j , and τ_j can be fitted using Eq. (5) and (7) in the second step. We recommend using at least three configurations with different compaction speeds and the same final FVC for the branch parameter fitting in order to cover the strain rate dependency.

4 APPLICATION OF THE VISCOUS EXP MODEL

4.1 MODEL CALIBRATION

The analytical *viscous exp* model is calibrated in two steps. At first, the parameters of the stiffness of the free spring E_0 are determined. In the second step, the remaining parameters, which define the stress in the branches, are identified. It is assumed that the stress of the fully relaxed state is only stored in the free spring. Thus, the stiffness E_0 can be determined independently of the branches. The relaxed stresses of the compaction experiments with the velocity 2 mm/min are used for the parameter fitting, in order to have four different fiber volume fractions. The values A and B in Eq. (6) are fitted with the experimental data in dependency of the final FVC. From Eq. (1), the strain can be calculated with the initial fiber volume fraction V_{f0} .

$$\epsilon = \frac{V_{f0}}{V_f} - 1 \quad (10)$$

Figure 4 shows the result of the parameter fitting for the free spring for the two tested materials. The relaxed stress from experimental data was plotted with the scatter of the corresponding configuration. The description of the stiffness E_0 in Eq. (6) predicted the relaxed stresses very well. The model curve was in very good agreement with the experimental data of both materials. Only the stress of the weave at 55% FVC was over-predicted and the stress of the NCF at 45% FVC was slightly under-predicted. Nevertheless, the curve remains within the scatter of the experimental data. The values of the parameter fitting are shown in Table 3.

Figure 4: Fitting of the model to the relaxed stresses of experimental data with 2 mm/min, including scatter for the weave material (WV) and the NCF

For the second step of the fitting procedure, we used configurations having different compaction velocities and the same final FVC. Three configurations were used to cover the strain rate dependent behavior of the material. The optimization algorithm provides the set of parameters having a minimum distance between the experimental and model curves according to Eq. (3). The resulting parameters which define the elastic branch stiffness from Eq. (8) and the branch relaxation times for both materials are provided in Table 3. The fitting parameters are shown for a model with three branches.

Figure 5 shows the three experimental input curves of the fitting algorithm with a final FVC of 55% and different compaction velocities with the corresponding model predictions. The model of the weave in Figure 5a exhibits a good level of accuracy during the compaction phase. Moreover, the model predicted the peak stresses

notably well, which is of special importance for tooling force analysis. During the relaxation, the model response matched the experiments very well for the first hundred seconds after the peak stress. In contrast, the model shows some deviations for the subsequent relaxation. For all velocities, a deviation can be seen from the experimental relaxed stress. The difference of the final stresses in the 2.0 mm/min compaction corresponded to the small deviation of the fit in Figure 4, at 55% FVC. The compaction at 1.0 mm/min exhibited minor deviations at the end of the relaxation. However, for higher compaction velocities, the model response diverged earlier from the experimental results. This behavior can be explained with the parameter fitting to the relaxed stresses in Figure 4. Since the model assumes that the relaxed stress is stored in the free spring, it is independent of the compaction velocity. The experimental data with different relaxed stresses cannot therefore be perfectly reproduced. Importantly, the relaxed stress of the model prediction was -0.375 MPa, which was still within the scatter area of the experimental data. The modeled material response of the NCF is compared with the experimental data in Figure 5b. Except for minor deviations at the beginning, the compaction phase of the model was in very good agreement with experimental data. Moreover, the peak stresses were predicted very well for all three compaction velocities. The stress relaxation was in good agreement with the experiments for the 2 mm/min and 1 mm/min compaction velocities, whereas the relaxation behavior for the highest velocity showed a deviation. As for the weave material, this can be explained with the strain rate-independent definition of E_0 .

Table 3: Fitting parameters of weave and NCF material for three-branch model

<i>Model parameter</i>	<i>Value weave material</i>	<i>Value NCF material</i>
A	$4.001 \cdot 10^{-3}$ MPa	$4.354 \cdot 10^{-4}$ MPa
B	$1.613 \cdot 10^{+1}$	$2.078 \cdot 10^{+1}$
a_1	$5.348 \cdot 10^{-3}$ MPa	$6.127 \cdot 10^{-3}$ MPa
b_1	$1.942 \cdot 10^{+1}$	$2.571 \cdot 10^{+1}$
a_2	$1.585 \cdot 10^{-1}$ MPa	$1.095 \cdot 10^{-8}$ MPa
b_2	9.274	$1.389 \cdot 10^{-2}$
a_3	$6.409 \cdot 10^{-3}$ MPa	$6.883 \cdot 10^{-3}$ MPa
b_3	$2.080 \cdot 10^{+1}$	$2.127 \cdot 10^{+1}$
τ_1	9.477 s	$1.452 \cdot 10^{+2}$ s
τ_2	$1.101 \cdot 10^{+2}$ s	$3.718 \cdot 10^{+1}$ s
τ_3	1.034 s	4.635 s

Figure 5: Fitting of the branch parameters to different compaction velocities for the three-branch model; (a) weave, (b) NCF

4.2 PARAMETER STUDY

We performed a sensitivity analysis in order to gain a better understanding of the model parameters. For this purpose, the optimum elastic and viscous parameters of the weave material in Table 3 were increased and decreased by 50%.

Figure 6 shows the results of the study, with every column representing one of the branches in the model. Each plot takes the modeled compaction curve from configuration WV_0.55-2 as a reference. The modification of the single parameters clearly shows the influence on different sections of the compaction response. Comparing the a_j values in the first row shows that a_1 influenced the peak stress and the early stress relaxation, whereas the parameter a_2 in the second branch influenced the relaxation behavior at later time points. However, a_3 did not have a significant influence on the characteristic of the curve. Varying the b_j parameters in the second row led to a similar behavior. Modifying b_1 strongly influenced the value of the peak stress. However, b_2 mostly affected the early stress relaxation. It is important to note that the b_j values were the only ones influencing the compaction phase for every branch. Varying the relaxation times τ_j showed that the first branch defined the beginning of the relaxation, and the second one defined the subsequent stress relaxation. In contrast, τ_3 seemed to have a minor influence on the compaction response. Generally, all relaxation times influenced the relaxation without having a significant influence on the compaction response or the peak stress.

The parameter study showed that different sections of the response curve can be modified individually by increasing or decreasing different variables. This study supports the outcome from the two tested materials, i.e., that very different behavior from strong to weak stress relaxation can be represented very accurately with the developed model.

Figure 6: Variation of elastic and viscous parameters for three branches of $\pm 50\%$ from the fitted optimum. All curves are plotted for 2 mm/min with 0.5 final FVC.

Interestingly, the third branch was only sensitive to an increased b_3 value. Moreover, it seems that the effect of increasing b_3 can also be achieved by a combination of other parameters. However, decreasing b_3 or varying the other values in the third branch had a minor effect on the model response. This finding indicated that the compaction behavior can also be modeled with only two branches. So, we repeated the fitting procedure for the weave with a different number of branches. The normalized total stress difference λ_{tot} of the three input curves was used to evaluate the quality of the fit. Table 4 compares the results of the objective function for one, two, three, and four branches. The comparison proves that the third branch has a minor influence on the model behavior. The model with two branches decreases the quality of the fit by 7.4% compared to three branches. However, further reduction to a single branch worsens the result significantly. The model with four branches shows a negligible improvement of the fit compared to three branches. Due to the high number of variables, the computational effort for the optimization increases significantly. For the following validation, we used three branches in order to obtain the best possible results with a reasonable amount of CPU effort.

Table 4: Total difference of the parameter fitting of the weave material for different number of branches N

N	λ_{tot}
1	$24.79 \cdot 10^{-3}$
2	$6.231 \cdot 10^{-3}$
3	$5.803 \cdot 10^{-3}$
4	$5.799 \cdot 10^{-3}$

4.3 MODEL VALIDATION AND DISCUSSION

For the derivation of the parameters in the branches, the three configurations 0.55-1, 0.55-2, and 0.55-5 from Table 1 were used for each material. The remaining experiments can thus be used for validating the model. Figure 7 shows the experimental results and the corresponding model predictions for all displacement-controlled configurations with the weave material. In general, the model with three branches predicted the compaction response of the woven material very well. During the compression phase, there was only a small deviation for configuration WV_0.50-5. The model and the experiments show a good agreement for the peak stresses for both low and high fiber volume fractions. However, deviations were observed in the relaxation phase. The modeled relaxation response was very accurate for configurations WV_0.50-2, WV_0.55-2, and WV_0.55-5. For lower fiber volume fraction values, as in configuration WV_0.45-2, the model relaxed the stresses too slowly. In contrast, the higher fiber volume fraction in configuration WV_0.60-2 causes an overly rapid stress relaxation. The final stresses in all configurations were in very good agreement with the experimental results. For the slower (configuration WV_0.50-5) and faster (configuration WV_0.50-1) compaction velocities with 50% FVC, the stress did not relax to the experimental values, which is due to the model assumption of a purely elastic free spring.

Figure 8 shows the mean experimental curve, including scatter, together with the results of the modeled stress response of the NCF material. The modeled compression phase was in very good agreement with experimental results, showing only small deviations at the beginning of the compaction. As for the woven fabric, the model predicted the peak stresses very well for all configurations. During the relaxation, the same effect as that of the weave can be observed. If the material was compacted to a low FVC, the model relaxed the stress too slowly, whereas the stress relaxation was too fast at a high final FVC. This could be explained with the different phases during the compaction as introduced in section 1. During the compaction of configurations NCF_0.45-2 and WV_0.45-2, larger voids remained in the preform without entering the third phase of sharp stress increase, whereas configurations NCF_0.60-2 and WV_0.60-2 exhibited stronger yarn deformation. This effect might be the cause for the deviation in the relaxation behavior. Another parameter could be introduced into the macroscopic model in order to cover the additional strain rate dependency during the stress relaxation. The relaxation of the model agrees very well with experimental data at 50% FVC for all velocities tested. The final stresses were in very good agreement with experimental results for all configurations, except for NCF_0.45-2. The deviation of the relaxed stress came from the fit of the free spring E_0 illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 7: Experimental data of the weave material tests for different compaction velocities and final FVC, including minimum and maximum scatter area and prediction of the viscous exp model

Figure 8: Experimental data of the NCF material tests for different compaction velocities and final FVC, including minimum and maximum scatter area and prediction of the viscous exp model

The formulation in Eq. (7) cannot be solved analytically for force boundary conditions used to calculate compaction strains. Nevertheless, the calculation of strains is possible in numerical simulations. The *viscous exp* model has been implemented in user material routine in ANSYS. Validation simulations were conducted on an 1D bar using a LINK180 element. The model was set up in ANSYS Mechanical APDL with a length which corresponds to the initial thickness of the test samples. The cross-sectional area of the bar element was set to the size of the specimens. Thus, resulting stresses can directly be compared with experimental data. One node was fully constrained, and a displacement or force boundary condition was applied to the second node.

Figure 9a shows the results of the numerical one-dimensional simulation and the experimental results of the force-controlled experiments at a 100 N/s compaction rate of the weave material. The numerical simulation predicts the behavior in the three phases of compaction, creeping, and spring-back very well. The compression in the first phase was in good agreement with the experiment and was only slightly over-estimated. The model also showed the creep of the material at a constant force, where the slope of the curve was less than the experimental one. However, the thickness at the end of the creep phase differed by 4.8% from the experiments. Moreover, the simulation predicted the spring-back of the material when the force was released. Although there was a difference in the increase of qualitative thickness, the final thickness was predicted very well, with a difference of 3.0% from the experimental value.

Figure 9b compares the numerical simulation with the force-controlled experiments of the weave at a 250 N/s compaction rate. As for the slower compaction rate, the three phases of the experiment can be seen. During the compaction, the predicted behavior agreed very well with the experimental results. The modeled creeping showed slightly higher displacements than the experimental data, with a deviation of 3.1% of the thickness at the end of this phase. Similar to the slower compaction, the spring-back showed the most significant difference in qualitative behavior. However, the difference in the final thickness compared to the experiments was 6.5%. For both tested configurations, the modeled thickness differed by between 3.0% and 6.5% from the experiments at the end of the creep and the spring-back. This model thus provides a powerful tool for predicting the thickness of preforms in force-controlled setups.

Figure 9: Experimental data for force-controlled experiments, including minimum and maximum scatter area and results of the model of the weave material; (a) slow compaction, (b) fast compaction

Figure 10a compares the modeled displacement response of the NCF with experimental data for the force-controlled configuration at a low force rate. The modeled compression phase was in excellent agreement with the experimental data. The following creep phase at a constant compaction pressure showed small deviations from the experiment, with a difference of 0.7% of the maximum displacement. The modeled thickness slightly decreases, but not as much as in the experiments. The predicted spring back was significantly lower than the experimental data. The experiment showed a spring back to 1.9mm when the force was released, whereas the model showed a spring back to only 2.2 mm.

Figure 10b shows the comparison of experimental and modeled data of the high force rate configuration of the NCF material. The observations from the comparison were very similar to the slower compaction. A good agreement during the compaction was followed by some deviations in the creep phase and significant differences for the spring back. The differences can be explained by the deviations of the displacement-controlled configuration NCF_0.60_2, because the preforms were compacted to approximately 59% FVC in the force-controlled setups. The comparison of NCF_0.60_2 in Figure 8 shows a very fast stress relaxation at the beginning and almost negligible time-dependent behavior of the model towards later times. The same behavior can be seen in Figure 10, where the thickness decreases too quickly at the beginning of the creep phase and shows too little time-dependent behavior during the further creep and the spring-back.

Figure 10: Experimental data for force-controlled experiments, including minimum and maximum scatter area and results of the model of the NCF material; (a) slow compaction, (b) fast compaction

Figure 11 is a comparison of the simulation results for the displacement-controlled and force-controlled experiments with the weave material. In Figure 11a, the thickness reduction is compared for both setups. The dashed line shows the displacement boundary condition of configuration WV_0.60-2. The continuous line is the simulation result of the force-controlled experiment at a 100 N/s compaction rate. The force-controlled curve shows a steeper slope at the beginning and slowly flattens until reaching a plateau after about 200 s. However, both curves converge to the same displacement value. The final thickness is the same for the displacement-controlled and force-controlled setups. Thus, according to Eq. (1), the final FVC is equal. Figure 11b compares the stresses in thickness direction over time for both configurations. The dashed line is the resulting stress from the numerical simulation of configuration WV_0.60-2. The continuous line is the stress boundary condition of the force-controlled simulation. The final stress at 700 s was almost equal, with -1.0 MPa for force-controlled and -0.98 MPa for displacement-controlled, respectively. The peak stress was at 101 s, whereas the constant stress of the force-controlled configuration was reached at 100 s. The peak stress of the displacement-controlled configuration more than doubled, with a value of -2.1 MPa. Thus, the resulting peak stress can be reduced by 50%

with slightly changing the evolution of the strain. In an RTM process, the challenge is to know the force which is necessary to achieve the desired FVC. As a result, the model developed in this paper makes it possible to design the process for minimizing peaks in tooling forces. It is possible either to design a force control or to adjust the displacement curve so as to avoid high peaks. This allows the use of a smaller press in the RTM process. This example clearly demonstrates the capabilities of the developed material model. Most of the existing models reviewed in section 1 divide between the compaction and relaxation phase, so the ramp time between the phases needs to be known. In the case of the force-controlled setup, Figure 11a shows a smooth transition between compaction and relaxation, thus making it impossible to define the beginning of relaxation. It can be assumed that stresses are relaxing at small strain rates which cannot be described by most of the models found in the literature.

Figure 11: Comparison of displacement (a) and stress (b) for displacement-controlled and force-controlled simulations of the weave material

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, we conducted compaction experiments with carbon fiber woven fabrics and NCF preforms on a universal testing machine. The influence of the machine deformation was able to be avoided in order to achieve a constant compaction velocity. We developed a novel formulation of a viscoelastic material model which describes compaction and relaxation in a single set of formulas. As a result, the model can be used for non-constant strain rates or force-controlled setups with a smooth transition between the two phases. The necessary number of branches in the model was defined using the results of a parameter study. We obtained very good agreement between the model stress response and the experimental tests for the two tested materials. By means of implementation into a finite element code, the model can be applied to force boundary conditions. We managed to predict the compression, including creep and spring back, satisfactorily. None of the known material models from the literature has been applied and validated for the prediction of creeping and spring back behavior. In addition to calculating the preform thickness, this method can also be applied to reduce tooling forces in RTM processes. We demonstrated that the peak compression stress could be eliminated for the characterized material. The maximum stress for achieving the same final FVC was able to be reduced by 50 % in the same process duration. The model was validated for two materials with very different compaction and relaxation behaviors. Together with the results of the parameter study, we believe that this model can be applied to a variety of fibrous preforms showing viscoelastic behavior.

In order to apply the model so as to predict tooling forces during the injection in RTM processes, the saturated wet material needs to be characterized. Moreover, the experimental setup and specimen preparation can be further improved to minimize the scatter. The experiments showed a different relaxed stress for preforms which were compressed to the same fiber volume content at different compaction velocities. The experiments with two different materials did not show a clear relation between strain rate and relaxed stress. Further investigations into this behavior will be necessary in order to improve the model. Since the model with two branches showed a nearly identical quality for the fit, it could be considered for further applications. In more complex numerical simulations, there might be an advantage in CPU time but an almost negligible loss in quality of the results. In order to be able to predict preform shapes of non-planar geometries, the model needs to be extended to a three-dimensional formulation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon2020 research program [project ID 821019]

REFERENCES

- [1] Dong C. Model development for the formation of resin-rich zones in composites processing. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2011;42(4):419–24.
- [2] Koutsonas S. Modelling race-tracking variability of resin rich zones on 90° composite 2.2 twill fibre curved plate. *Composites Science and Technology* 2018;168:448–59.
- [3] Darrow DA, Smith LV. Isolating Components of Processing Induced Warpage in Laminated Composites. *Journal of Composite Materials* 2002;36(21):2407–19.
- [4] Huang CK, Yang SY. Warping in advanced composite tools with varying angles and radii. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 1997;28(9-10):891–3.
- [5] Brauner C, Bauer S, Herrmann AS. Analysing process-induced deformation and stresses using a simulated manufacturing process for composite multispar flaps. *Journal of Composite Materials* 2015;49(4):387–402.
- [6] Robitaille F, Gauvin R. Compaction of textile reinforcements for composites manufacturing. I: Review of experimental results. *Polym. Compos.* 1998;19(2):198–216.
- [7] Bickerton S, Buntain MJ, Somashekar AA. The viscoelastic compression behavior of liquid composite molding preforms. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2003;34(5):431–44.
- [8] Chen B, Lang EJ, Chou T-W. Experimental and theoretical studies of fabric compaction behavior in resin transfer molding. *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 2001;317(1-2):188–96.
- [9] Wei K, Liang D, Mei M, Wang D, Yang X, Qu Z. Preforming behaviors of carbon fiber fabrics with different contents of binder and under various process parameters. *Composites Part B: Engineering* 2019;166:221–32.
- [10] Mbakop RS, Lebrun G, Brouillette F. Experimental analysis of the planar compaction and preforming of unidirectional flax reinforcements using a thin paper or flax mat as binder for the UD fibers. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2018;109:604–14.
- [11] Grieser T, Mitschang P. Investigation of the compaction behavior of carbon fiber NCF for continuous preforming processes. *Polym. Compos.* 2017;38(11):2609–25.
- [12] Chen B, Cheng AH-D, Chou T-W. A nonlinear compaction model for fibrous preforms. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2001;32(5):701–7.
- [13] Wang D. Mesoscopic modeling and simulation on the forming process of textile composites: Dissertation; 2019.

- [14] Robitaille F, Gauvin R. Compaction of textile reinforcements for composites manufacturing. III: Reorganization of the fiber network. *Polym. Compos.* 1999;20(1):48–61.
- [15] Kelly PA, Umer R, Bickerton S. Viscoelastic response of dry and wet fibrous materials during infusion processes. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2006;37(6):868–73.
- [16] Sousa P, Lomov SV, Ivens J. Methodology of dry and wet compressibility measurement. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2020;128:105672.
- [17] Kabachi MA, Stettler L, Arreguin S, Ermanni P. Concurrent characterization of through-thickness permeability and compaction of fiber reinforcements. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2021;141(9):106203.
- [18] Bickerton S, Kelly PA. *Modelling the Viscoelastic Compression Behaviour of Fibrous Reinforcing Fabrics*. Baltimore; 2002.
- [19] Lee SH, Han JH, Kim SY, Youn JR, Song YS. Compression and Relaxation Behavior of Dry Fiber Preforms for Resin Transfer Molding. *Journal of Composite Materials* 2010;44(15):1801–20.
- [20] Kim YR, McCarthy SP, Fanucci JP. Compressibility and relaxation of fiber reinforcements during composite processing. *Polym. Compos.* 1991;12(1):13–9.
- [21] Schapery RA. On the characterization of nonlinear viscoelastic materials. *Polym. Eng. Sci.* 1969;9(4):295–310.
- [22] Haj-Ali RM, Muliana AH. Numerical finite element formulation of the Schapery non-linear viscoelastic material model. *Int. J. Numer. Meth. Engng.* 2004;59(1):25–45.
- [23] Varna J, Pupure L, Joffe R. Incremental forms of Schapery's model: convergence and inversion to simulate strain controlled ramps. *Mech Time-Depend Mater* 2016;20(4):535–52.
- [24] Kaliske M, Rothert H. Formulation and implementation of three-dimensional viscoelasticity at small and finite strains. *Computational Mechanics* 1997;19(3):228–39.
- [25] Kelly PA. A viscoelastic model for the compaction of fibrous materials. *Journal of the Textile Institute* 2011;102(8):689–99.
- [26] Somashekar AA, Bickerton S, Bhattacharyya D. Modelling the viscoelastic stress relaxation of glass fibre reinforcements under constant compaction strain during composites manufacturing. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2012;43(7):1044–52.
- [27] Yenilmez B, Caglar B, Sozer EM. Viscoelastic modeling of fiber preform compaction in vacuum infusion process. *Journal of Composite Materials* 2017;51(30):4189–203.
- [28] Danzi M, Schneeberger C, Ermanni P. A model for the time-dependent compaction response of woven fiber textiles. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2018;105:180–8.
- [29] Bickerton S, Kelly PA. Application of a Complete Tooling Force Analysis for Simulation of Liquid Composite Moulding Processes. *KEM* 2007;334-335:17–20.
- [30] Bickerton S, Buntain MJ. Modeling forces generated within rigid liquid composite molding tools. Part B: Numerical analysis. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2007;38(7):1742–54.
- [31] Gupta A, Kelly PA, Bickerton S, Walbran WA. Simulating the effect of temperature elevation on clamping force requirements during rigid-tool Liquid Composite Moulding processes. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2012;43(12):2221–9.
- [32] Walbran WA, Verleye B, Bickerton S, Kelly PA. Prediction and experimental verification of normal stress distributions on mould tools during Liquid Composite Moulding. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2012;43(1):138–49.

- [33] Belnoue JP-H, Nixon-Pearson OJ, Thompson AJ, Ivanov DS, Potter KD, Hallett SR. Consolidation-Driven Defect Generation in Thick Composite Parts. *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering* 2018;140(7):1343.
- [34] Xiong H, Hamila N, Boisse P. Consolidation Modeling during Thermoforming of Thermoplastic Composite Prepregs. *Materials (Basel)* 2019;12(18).
- [35] Merotte J, Simacek P, Advani SG. Resin flow analysis with fiber preform deformation in through thickness direction during Compression Resin Transfer Molding. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2010;41(7):881–7.
- [36] Pillai KM, Tucker CL, Phelan FR. Numerical simulation of injection/compression liquid composite molding. Part 2: preform compression. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2001;32(2):207–20.
- [37] Martin FA, Warrior NA, Simacek P, Advani S, Hughes A, Darlington R et al. Simulation and Validation of Injection-Compression Filling Stage of Liquid Moulding with Fast Curing Resins. *Appl Compos Mater* 2019;26(1):41–63.
- [38] Verleye B, Walbran WA, Bickerton S, Kelly PA. Simulation and experimental validation of force controlled compression resin transfer molding. *Journal of Composite Materials* 2011;45(7):815–29.
- [39] Thompson AJ, McFarlane JR, Belnoue JP-H, Hallett SR. Numerical modelling of compaction induced defects in thick 2D textile composites. *Materials & Design* 2020:109088.
- [40] Hexcel. G0926 D 1304 TCT INJECTEX E01 2F: Data Sheet; 2020.
- [41] Teijin. Tenax Filament Yarn: Data Sheet.
- [42] Lomov SV, Verpoest I, Peeters T, Roose D, Zako M. Nesting in textile laminates: geometrical modelling of the laminate. *Composites Science and Technology* 2003;63(7):993–1007.
- [43] Chen B. Compaction of woven-fabric preforms: nesting and multi-layer deformation. *Composites Science and Technology* 2000;60(12-13):2223–31.